

**BEHAVIOR OF THE ENERGY PROPERTIES OF WOODEN
BRIQUETTES FROM THE COMBINED ACTION OF THE PRESSURE
AND SATURATION OF ITS MICROSTRUCTURE WITH
CARBONACEOUS SOLIDS**

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ABSTRACT

It is known that the increase in energy density of wood can also be obtained from the production of briquettes from this biomass residue. Due to the high compaction of these residues, the briquettes obtained from this have energy density values of two to three times the value obtained for wood and up to seven times that of the residue itself. The main objective of this work was to investigate, on an exploratory basis, the combined effect of pressure and the addition of carbonaceous solids to the wood structure, on the behavior of the energetic properties, in particular, the energetic density of this material. Different wood residues of unknown origin in the form of branches harvested on the UFR campus were machined with dimensions close to those compacted at different pressures. The powder residues obtained from turning these branches with a particle size ≤ 0.85 mm were compacted at pressures of up to 300 MPa. The machined samples and briquettes produced at different pressures were characterized via

immediate analysis, determination of calorific value and measurements of bulk density and energy. The results showed that the combined effect of pressure and the addition of carbonaceous solids to the wood structure significantly influenced the behavior of the bulk and energetic densities of this material. Comparing the results, it was possible to identify in the samples under the aforementioned effect a percentage increase in energy density of up to 49.4%.

Keywords: Biomass; Measure briquettes; Energy Properties; Carbonaceous Solids.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is known that wood used as an energy source has carbon contents of approximately 50% in its structure. This is due to its loss during the period in which it was standing as a tree, after its felling as wood or in its processing, storage and transport operations [1,2] . An alternative to minimize this carbon loss in wood and improve its energy properties is to manufacture briquettes from this biomass and saturate its microstructure with carbon in the form of carbonaceous solids. From the point of view of pressure, the compaction of these residues is high. The briquettes obtained from this have energy density values of two to three times the value obtained for wood and up to five times that of the residue itself [3,4] . From the point of view of addition of carbonaceous solids, it is very likely that the voids or pores present in the briquettes are filled with this material. Soon there will be an increase in the carbon content and consequently the energy density in these materials. The main objective of this work was to investigate the effect of the behavior of the energetic properties of briquettes from the combined action of pressure and saturation of carbonaceous solids on the microstructure of this material. Powder residues of unknown origin with particle size ≤ 0.85 mm were compacted at pressures up to 300 MPa. Then half of the samples produced were immersed in a liquid solution enriched with carbon in the form of carbonaceous solids until saturation. The other half were not immersed. Comparing the results, it was possible to identify a percentage increase in the energy density of up to 49.4% in the saturated briquettes. In addition, from an energy point of view, the possibility of enriching the microstructure of any type of wood with carbon opens a path where not only wood, but any other type of solid biomass such as those presented in the literature can also be enriched. The perspective one has from this fact is: a) a significant addition of value to solid biomass residues; b) a great reduction in the disposal of these materials as garbage in the regions where they are generated and, consequently, a contribution to the sustainability of these regions ; c) an important contribution to the reduction of deforestation in

several regions of the country, such as the Center-West, in particular, the state of Mato Grosso, where it is very difficult to implement new forest plantations .

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. MATERIALS

The biomasses used were any wood regardless of its origin and specific characteristics, randomly harvested from the soil of the Campus of the Federal University of Rondonópolis. Samples of these materials were machined and the granulometry of the powder produced from the machining of these materials was measured using the Electromagnetic Stirrer for Sieve shown in figure 1. The granulometry greater than or equal to 0.85 mm was that used for the production of compacts.

Figure 1 . Electromagnetic Stirrer for Sieve.

Source: Authors.

2.2. METHODOLOGY

The starting powders of unknown wood used to manufacture the briquettes were always from the same batch. Five different pressures, that is, 100 MPa, 150 MPa, 200 MPa, 250 MPa and 300 MPa were used for compacting the powders via the compaction system shown in Fig

2. Eighty were compacted at each pressure, making a total of four hundred briquettes manufactured. After every eighty samples produced, forty remained as manufactured and forty were immersed in a liquid solution enriched with 65% carbonaceous solids until saturation. To saturate the sample with the solution of carbonaceous solids, it was first necessary to remove all the initial moisture contained inside the briquettes (compact) and machined samples. For this, they were placed in an oven at $105^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$. At each period of time, the samples were weighed until, according to the technical standard ABNT NBR 14929:2009, the difference between the current and previous measurements was not greater than 0.5%. This same procedure was used in the drying analysis of the samples after they were saturated with the liquid solution (65% of carbonaceous solids) produced in the Laboratories of the Mechanical Engineering Course at UFR.

Figure 2. Compression system: a) Die where the wood powders were inserted into its cylindrical cavity and upper and lower punches used to compact it under different pressures: b) Traction/Compression machine used to produce the cylindrical briquettes from of the compaction of the powders that were inserted in the matrix cavity.

Source: Authors.

Figure 3 shows the typical appearance of the produced compacts. Unlike light briquettes, those with a dark color are those saturated with carbonaceous solids. Next, all the manufactured specimens were characterized by immediate analysis, calorific power, apparent density and energy density. The immediate analysis was carried out based on ABNT NBR 8112/1986, the calorific value estimated according to the equation by PARIKH, CHANNIWALA and GHOSAL (2005) and the apparent density measured according to ABNT

NBR 6922/1981 in a container with volume equivalent to a box with internal dimensions of (22.90 x 22.90 x 22.90) mm.

Figure 3. Typical briquettes produced at different compaction pressures with or without the addition of carbonaceous solids.

Source: Authors

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the results for the briquettes and the machined sample that were not saturated with carbonaceous solids. As can be seen, the compacted powder mass of the briquettes increased as the pressure also increased. The mass of any one of the briquettes was always greater than the measurement for the machined sample. This indicates that while the pores of the latter remain empty, those present in the briquettes are gradually being reduced and filled with dust. Therefore, it is to be expected that all briquettes present higher energy density values than those obtained for the machined sample.

Another interesting aspect to be observed in briquettes is the effect of pressure on the reduction of powder and pore size. In order to adapt to this effect, the granulometry of the starting powder (≤ 0.85 mm) must always be smaller than or equal to the pore size where it is being inserted. This indicates that starting powders during your compaction are being reduced. The main factor responsible for the increase in compacted density values was pressure, through its simultaneous action in reducing the size of the powders and the pores where they were inserted.

Table 1. Results of briquettes that were not saturated with carbonaceous solids.

SAMPLES	DIMENSIONS [mm]		MASS [g]	DENSITY [g/cm ³]
	DIAMETER	HEIGHT		
AB100SC	25.03 ± 0.05	20.30 ± 0.03	10.0238 ± 0.0010	1.0037
AB150SC	25.00 ± 0.04	23.00 ± 0.10	11.3011 ± 0.0030	1.0009
AB200SC	24.90 ± 0.04	23.50 ± 0.08	11.4647 ± 0.0003	1.0019
AB250SC	24.90 ± 0.04	23.00 ± 0.08	11.7835 ± 0.0004	1.0521
AB300SC	24.90 ± 0.03	23.03 ± 0.06	12.0554 ± 0.0012	1.0750

Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXSC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) SC - without addition of carbonaceous.

Table 2 presents the results for the briquettes and the machined sample that were saturated with carbonaceous solids. As can be seen in the present study, the increase in the density of the samples, whether or not they are saturated with carbonaceous, is associated with the filling of their pores with wood residue dust and/or carbonaceous solids, respectively. The pores not filled with wood dust present in the compacted briquettes at each pressure were filled with carbonaceous solids until their size was smaller than the pore. According to the results presented in Table 2, it is noted that in all samples the increase in the mass of carbonaceous deposited in the pores generated an increase in the density of these materials. Unlike the briquettes that were not saturated with carbonaceous and depended only on the pressure to increase their density, here it also depends on the sum of the densities of wood dust and carbonaceous versus their respective percentages distributed in the microstructure of the briquettes. Comparing the density values of the machined sample with those obtained for the briquettes, it is noted that the increase in this property in these materials can reach twice that obtained for the machined one. The compact produced under 300 MPa is an example of this. For a practically fixed volume there was an addition of mass to it. The pressure used to compact the briquettes and the amount of carbonaceous solids distributed in the microstructure of these materials were the main factors responsible for the increase in their densities.

Table 2. Results of briquettes that were saturated with carbonaceous solids.

SAMPLES	DIMENSIONS [mm]		MASS [g]	DENSITY [g/cm ³]
	DIAMETER	HEIGHT		
AB100SC	25.05 ± 0.03	21.65 ± 0.08	11.5054 ± 0.0015	1.1010

AB150SC	24.95 ± 0.03	24.60 ± 0.05	13.2512 ± 0.0025	1.1018
AB200SC	24.90 ± 0.04	24.70 ± 0.08	13.5004 ± 0.0060	1.1224
AB250SC	24.90 ± 0.05	24.65 ± 0.05	13.5087 ± 0.0050	1.1254
AB300SC	24.95 ± 0.04	24.70 ± 0.05	14.7009 ± 0.0070	1.2173
Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXSC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) SC - without addition of carbonaceous.				

Tables 3 and 4 show the results of the immediate analysis of the briquettes with and without the addition of carbonaceous solids. Comparing the results among themselves, it is observed that the presence of carbonaceous solids in the briquettes contributed both to the reduction of their ability to absorb moisture and to the significant increase in the fixed carbon content in the briquettes compacted at 200 MPa. Additionally, it was also observed in the microstructure of the briquettes a relationship between the presence of carbonaceous solids and the reduction of moisture in these materials. Moisture content was reduced in briquettes saturated with carbonaceous solids. From these facts, especially the one related to the increase in the fixed carbon content, it is to be expected that the calorific value and energy density values are also significantly increased in the compressed briquettes at 200 MPa.

Table 3. Results of the immediate analysis of the briquettes that were not immersed in the solution enriched with carbonaceous solids.

RESULTS OF IMMEDIATE ANALYSIS				
BRIQUETTES	%MOISTURE	%VOLATILES	%ASHES	%FIXED CARBON
AB100SC	7.0113	91.1860	0.6505	8.1635
AB150SC	6.3829	93.1579	0.3949	6.4473
AB200SC	3.3172	89.1822	0.3128	10.5050
AB250SC	1.2397	86.3340	1.9866	11.6794
AB300SC	1.6420	95.6159	1.8654	2.5187
Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXSC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) SC - without addition of carbonaceous.				

Table 4. Results of the immediate analysis of the briquettes that were immersed in the solution enriched with carbonaceous solids.

RESULTS OF IMMEDIATE ANALYSIS				
BRIQUETTE	%MOISTURE	%VOLATILE	%ASHES	%FIXED CARBON

S		S		
AB100CC	1.9745	85.7270	0.3595	13.9135
AB150CC	5.6969	84.8588	0.6044	14.5368
AB200CC	3.1430	92.7311	0.3766	6.8923
AB250CC	1.1097	86.5750	2.4767	10.9482
AB300CC	1.5420	93.6058	1.9469	4.4473

Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXCC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) CC - with addition of carbonaceous.

In Tables 5 and 6 it is possible to verify the bulk density values of the briquettes without and with addition of carbonaceous. It is observed that the values of this property in all samples saturated with carbonaceous were higher than those presented for those not saturated with this material. In addition, all briquettes had a bulk density greater than that measured in the machined sample. The application of pressure reduced the initial particle size of the powders and consequently increased the bulk density of the briquettes. For the same volume, the smaller the size of the powder, the greater the quantity available for deposit in that volume. When considering this fact under the effect of the presence of carbonaceous solids dissolved in the briquettes, it is noted that this material contributed to the bulk density being greater than that measured only under the effect of pressure. The size of the pressed powder has been reduced. All the briquettes were saturated and among the compacted ones, those manufactured at lower pressures are those where there was a greater amount of pores not yet filled with dust, but with carbonaceous. This was more expressive in the compressed briquettes under 100 MPa and 150 MPa.

Table 5. Bulk density values for compacted briquettes from dry powder that have not been saturated with carbonaceous solids.

SAMPLE	BULK DENSITY [kg/m ³]
AB100SC	316.6258
AB150SC	347.1562
AB200SC	374.1636
AB250SC	344.8075
AB300SC	289.4323

Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXSC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) SC - without addition of carbonaceous.

Table 6. Bulk density values for compacted briquettes from dry powder that have been saturated with carbonaceous solids.

SAMPLE	BULK DENSITY [kg/m ³]
AB100CC	442.1912
AB150CC	446.2682
AB200CC	464.4949
AB250CC	416.8608
AB300CC	414.5699

Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXCC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) CC - with addition of carbonaceous.

Tables 7 and 8 show the values of the energetic properties obtained for both machined and compacted samples, with and without the addition of carbonaceous solids. Comparing the mass results of the machined sample with those presented for the briquettes, it is noted that the increase in mass significantly influenced the increase in the energy density of these materials. Regardless of whether the percentage by mass of wood dust and/or carbonaceous particles added to the microstructure of the briquettes was different or not, their total sum was the main factor responsible for the increase in energy density in these materials. In the present study, the highest values obtained for this property were 8083.87 MJ/m³ and 8195.51 MJ/m³ for briquettes compressed at 100 MPa and 150 MPa respectively. This pressure range is within that used in industrial briquette machines and this is very interesting from a commercial point of view.

Table 7. Values of calorific value and energy density for briquettes compacted from dry powder that were not saturated with carbonaceous solids.

SAMPLE	HEAT POWER [Kcal/Kg]		ENERGY DENSITY [MJ/m ³]	
	PCI	pcs	PCI	pcs
AB100SC	4083.0546	4086,2892	5409.0768	5413,3618
AB150SC	4011.9620	4015.1966	5827,3806	5832.0789
AB200SC	4206.8976	4210,1322	6585.8999	6590.9636
AB250SC	4196.9050	4200.1396	6054,7684	6059.4349
AB300SC	3768.8058	3772.0404	4563.9660	4567.8831

Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXSC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) SC - without addition of carbonaceous.

Tab. 8. Calorific value and energy density values for compacted briquettes from dry powder that have been saturated with carbonaceous solids.

SAMPLE	HEAT POWER [Kcal/Kg]		ENERGY DENSITY [MJ/m ³]	
	PCI	pcs	PCI	pcs
AB100CC	4366.1255	4369,3601	8077,8907	8083,8751
AB150CC	4385.9969	4389,2315	8189.4722	8195.5118
AB200CC	4033,7036	4036.9382	7839,2871	7845.5734
AB250CC	4143,1820	4146,4166	7226.3122	7231.9538
AB300CC	3856.7370	3859.9716	6689,7432	6695.3538

Note: 1- Samples named ABXXXCC are identified by: a) AB - briquette; b) XXX – pressure; c) CC - with addition of carbonaceous.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The amount and size of pores distributed in the microstructure of the briquettes depends on the pressure and are probably larger and smaller, respectively, than those presented in the machined samples.

The presence of carbonaceous solids in the structure of all samples increased the energy density of these materials. In the case of machined from 3116.5444 MJ/m³ to 3466.877 and briquettes from 5413.3618 MJ/m³ to 8083.8751 MJ/m³. This represents a percentage increase of 11.5% and 49.5% respectively.

While in the machined sample the increase in energetic properties is due only to the addition of carbonaceous solids to its structure, in the briquettes the aforementioned properties depended mainly on the sum of the particulate mass, that is, the sum of the carbonaceous solids with the wood powders.

In the present work, the saturation of wood residues of different unknown species, mixed or not with each other, via carbon in the form of carbonaceous solids, was effective. Furthermore, from an energy point of view, the possibility of enriching the microstructure of any type of wood with carbon opens up a path where not only wood, but any other type of solid biomass can also be enriched. The perspective one has from this fact is one of: a) significant addition of value to solid biomass residues; b) great reduction in the disposal of these materials

as garbage in the regions where they are generated and, consequently, a contribution to the sustainability of these regions ; c) important contribution to the reduction of deforestation in various regions of the country such as the Center-West in particular, the state of Mato Grosso where the difficulty is great in implementing new forest plantations.

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